

Synthesis, physicochemical and antibacterial studies of transition metal chelates involving tetradentate Schiff base

M. K. Rahangdale, A. R. Yaul, G. B. Pethe and A. S. Aswar*

Department of Chemistry, Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati-444 602, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : aswaranand@gmail.com

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Abstract : The complexes of VO^{IV}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, MoO₂^{VI} and UO₂^{VI} with tetradentate Schiff base ligand derived from 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone and carbohydrazide have been prepared. These complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, UV-Vis and IR spectroscopy, magnetic measurements and thermal analysis. The complexes were found to be quite stable and decomposition of the complexes ended with respective metal oxide as a final product. Various kinetic and thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated from the thermal decomposition data. Infrared spectral study show that the ligand behaves as dibasic tetradentate in nature in all the complexes. The solid state electrical conductivity of these compounds has been measured in their compressed pellet form and all the compounds showed semiconducting behaviour as their conductivity increases with increase in temperature. The Schiff base and its metal complexes have been screened for their antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. typhi*, *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis* by cup plate method. The metal complexes were shown to possess more antibacterial activity than the free ligand.

Keywords : Schiff base, complexes, dc electrical conductivity, TGA, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

Schiff bases play an important role in inorganic chemistry as they are easily prepared by a simple one-pot condensation of a carbonyl compound and primary amines and form stable complexes with most transition metal ions. The development of the field of bioinorganic chemistry has increased interest in Schiff base complexes, since it has been recognized that many of these complexes may serve as models for bioinorganic important species^{1,2}. Ligands derived from substituted carbohydrazone have played an important part in revealing the preferred coordination geometries of metal complexes and have valuable contribution in the coordination chemistry due to their preparative accessibility, diversity and structural variability. Of particular interest have been those involving higher valent metal ions since they reveal surprising molecular diversity not only in coordination geometry but in more subtle changes in the ligands^{3,4}. The carbohydrazones and their complexes with transition metal ions have been well documented in the literature as good therapeutic, antibacterial, anticonvulsant, pharmacologi-

cal and catalytic agents⁵⁻⁷. The impetus for the preparation of the metal derivatives of Schiff base of carbohydrazide and substituted hydroxyacetophenone has come from the desire to form simple mononuclear complexes for their physicochemical characterization and structural elucidation. Schiff bases and their complexes derived from carbohydrazone, semicarbazones, hydrazones and thioicarbazonones possesses a broad spectrum of medicinal properties⁸⁻¹⁰.

To the best of our knowledge, only a few reports¹¹⁻¹³ have been observed which include the hydroxyacetophenone Schiff bases, hence it was thought worthwhile to synthesise new Schiff base derived from hydroxyacetophenone and carbohydrazide and its complexes. In the present paper, we report the synthesis, antimicrobial and thermal studies of VO^{IV}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, MoO₂^{VI} and UO₂^{VI} complexes with Schiff base ligand derived from 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone and carbohydrazide. The structural features of the Schiff base and its metal complexes have been studied by various spectral and analytical techniques.

Results and discussion

The symmetrical tetradentate Schiff base ligand 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone carbohydrazone (H_2L) was prepared by the condensation of 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone and carbohydrazide gives the desired Schiff base in high yields and purity. The elemental analysis and physical data of the ligand and its coordination complexes are given in Table 1. All the complexes are coloured solids, air stable and insoluble in common organic solvents, such as ethanol, methanol, chloroform and acetone, but completely soluble in DMF and DMSO. The elemental analysis suggests 1 : 1 metal : ligand stoichiometry and is in good agreement with those values calculated from proposed formula.

IR spectra :

The coordination sites of the ligand involved in bonding with the metal ion have been determined by careful comparison of the IR spectra of the complexes with that

of the parent ligand. The Schiff base shows a medium intensity band at 2927 cm^{-1} due to intramolecularly hydrogen bonded $\nu(\text{OH})$. The absence of this band in the spectra complexes indicates deprotonation of the phenolic group and coordination of the Schiff base to metal ions through an oxygen atom. This is further supported by the upward shifting of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ phenolic band by $28-13\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of complexes from 1272 cm^{-1} , suggesting the coordination of phenolic oxygen with the metal ion. The IR spectrum of ligand shows a strong absorption at 3251 and 1720 cm^{-1} due to $\text{N}-\text{H}$ and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups respectively. The position of both the bands remains nearly same in spectra of complexes indicating their non-involvement in complexation¹⁴. The ligand spectrum exhibits a strong band at 1607 cm^{-1} due to stretching vibration of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ group. In the spectra of complexes this band shifted to lower frequency, suggesting that the azomethine nitrogen involve in coordination¹⁵. In ligand spectrum the band appear at 950 cm^{-1} due is to the $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$ group

Table 1. The proposed composition, formula weight, colour, elemental analysis and electrical conductivity of compounds

Proposed composition of the compounds	Formula weight	Colour	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Electrical conductivity ($\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$)
			C	H	N	M	
H_2L	395.23	Golden brown	64.72 (64.64)	9.21 (9.04)	16.87 (16.75)	-	9.21×10^{-13}
$[\text{VO}(\text{L})].\text{H}_2\text{O}$	480.19	Sapphire ice	51.58 (51.94)	3.23 (3.36)	11.57 (11.67)	10.46 (10.61)	5.65×10^{-7}
$[\text{Mn}(\text{L}).2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	486.20	Misty vale	51.12 (51.24)	3.30 (3.32)	11.32 (11.52)	11.18 (11.30)	4.56×10^{-10}
$[\text{Fe}(\text{L}).\text{H}_2\text{O}.\text{Cl}]$	504.55	Lemon grass	49.14 (49.21)	3.18 (3.20)	11.00 (11.10)	11.00 (11.07)	3.78×10^{-7}
$[\text{Co}(\text{L}).2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	490.20	Brown	50.56 (50.78)	3.22 (3.29)	11.31 (11.43)	11.98 (12.02)	5.10×10^{-9}
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}).2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	489.96	Waking earth	50.60 (50.81)	3.23 (3.29)	11.30 (11.43)	11.87 (11.98)	5.25×10^{-11}
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}).2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	494.72	Bottle olives	50.12 (50.27)	3.21 (3.26)	11.22 (11.32)	12.56 (12.83)	4.02×10^{-8}
$[\text{Zn}(\text{L}).2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	496.64	Kesarmilk	50.00 (50.07)	3.20 (3.25)	11.18 (11.28)	13.13 (13.16)	7.06×10^{-10}
$[\text{Cd}(\text{L}).2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	543.67	Faint yellow	45.28 (45.38)	2.78 (2.97)	10.10 (10.31)	20.28 (20.67)	2.85×10^{-7}
$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{L})]$	523.17	Surf green	47.23 (47.31)	3.05 (3.08)	10.53 (10.71)	18.28 (18.34)	6.09×10^{-7}
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{L})]$	665.26	Orange essence	36.43 (36.54)	2.31 (2.42)	8.34 (8.42)	35.65 (35.78)	6.83×10^{-7}

which shifted to the higher frequency by 65–36 cm^{-1} in the spectra of complexes also supports the involvement of the azomethine nitrogen atom in the coordination with the metal ion¹⁶. In the spectra of complexes, weak bands appears in the 556–598 and 445–495 cm^{-1} range can be attributed to $\nu(\text{M-O})$ and $\nu(\text{M-N})$ vibrations, respectively¹⁷. In the spectra of Mn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes the appearance of broad band of low intensity in the range 3380–3470 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to stretching vibrations of OH group of water molecules. Besides this, complexes also show bands in the range 1575–1695 and 850–885 cm^{-1} assignable to $\delta\gamma(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ and $\delta\omega(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ respectively for coordinated water molecules. The uranyl complex exhibits a strong band at 915 cm^{-1} and medium intensity band at 835 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ mode respectively¹⁸. Dioxomolybdenum(VI) complex shows band at 899 cm^{-1} due to symmetric and at 923 cm^{-1} due to asymmetric stretching frequency of *cis*- MoO_2 ¹⁹. The MoO_2^{VI} prefers to form a *cis* configuration due to maximum utilization of the $d\pi$ group. In the oxovanadium(IV) complex, the strong band at $\sim 965 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ modes. The infrared spectral data suggest that the Schiff base coordinated in its dianionic form to the metal, through phenolic oxygen and imine nitrogen atoms.

Electronic spectra and magnetic studies :

Electronic spectral data and magnetic susceptibility measurements have been used to establish the geometry of the metal complexes. The electronic spectrum of VO^{IV} complex shows three absorption bands at 895, 530 and 372 nm which may be assigned to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E_1$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$, transitions, respectively, in a square pyramidal geometry. The room temperature magnetic moment for the VO^{IV} complex was found to be 1.72 B.M., which is close to the spin only magnetic moment for one unpaired electron. The electronic spectrum of the Mn^{II} complex exhibits three weak bands in the normally expected regions for Mn^{II} octahedral structure. The bands at 585, 430 and 378 nm, are assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}({}^4G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}, {}^4E_g({}^4G)$, transitions, respectively, in an octahedral field. The observed magnetic moment 5.91 B.M is close to the spin only value for five unpaired electrons (5.92 B.M.) indicating

that complex is high spin octahedral. The electronic spectrum of Fe^{III} complex shows three bands at 758, 645 and 445 nm which are assigned to ${}^6A_{1g}(\text{S}) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(\text{G})$, ${}^6A_{1g}(\text{S}) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(\text{G})$ and ${}^6A_{1g}(\text{S}) \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(\text{G})$, transitions, respectively towards octahedral geometry around the Fe^{III} ion. The Fe^{III} complex exhibits a magnetic moment of 5.83 B.M. at room temperature value in the range accepted for octahedral geometry with five unpaired electrons^{20,21}. The cobalt(II) complex shows three bands at 995, 945 and 598 nm assigned to the ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(\text{F})$, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(\text{P})$, transitions, respectively. The magnetic moment value is found to be 5.20 B.M., which is in good agreement with high spin octahedral geometry. Since, spin only value for three unpaired electrons is only 3.99 B.M., the high value in the present case may be attributed to orbital contribution. The octahedral geometry was further supported by its nephelauxetic ratio ($\nu_2/\nu_1 = 1.3$) which is found to be less than 2 indicating partial covalent character in the metal-ligand bond. The electronic spectrum of Ni^{II} complex shows three bands at 967, 588 and 397 nm which may be safely assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\text{P})$, transitions, respectively for an octahedral geometry around Ni^{II} ion. This is further supported by the observed magnetic moment 2.88 B.M., which is in the expected range 2.80–3.30 B.M. for the octahedral geometry. The electronic spectrum of Cu^{II} complex displayed bands at 696, 658 and 612 nm assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, transitions, respectively in a distorted octahedral geometry²². Cu^{II} complex exhibits a magnetic moment 1.83 B.M., which is very close to the spin only value for one unpaired electron suggesting octahedral geometry around the Cu^{II} ion²³. The slightly higher value of the magnetic moment might be due to orbital contribution. The Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , MoO_2^{VI} and UO_2^{VI} complexes are found to be diamagnetic as expected and do not show any d-d transitions due to the absence of any unpaired electrons. On the basis of physicochemical data and literature survey, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes have tetrahedral geometry^{24,25} whereas MoO_2^{VI} and UO_2^{VI} complexes have octahedral geometry.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

Thermal analysis has proved to be useful in determin-

ing the types of water content in complexes and their thermal stability and the decomposition mode under a controlled heating rate. In the present study the decomposition of ligand (H_2L) and its complexes takes place in two stages as shown in Fig. 1. The VO^{IV} complex lose its weight in the temperature range 110–125 °C corresponding to the loss of one lattice water molecule²⁶. [% wt. loss, obs./calcd.; VO^{IV} : 3.88/3.71]. The complexes of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} show weight loss

of two coordinated water molecules in the temperature range 110–200 °C, while Fe^{III} complex loose one coordinated water molecule and chloride ion in this temperature range. [% wt. loss, obs./calcd.; Mn^{II} : 7.41/7.37; Co^{II} : 7.35/7.28; Ni^{II} : 7.41/7.35; Cu^{II} : 7.39/7.28; Zn^{II} : 7.34/7.25 and Cd^{II} : 6.75/6.62, VO^{IV} : 3.88/3.71, Fe^{III} : 3.90/3.57; 7.13/7.02 (chloride ion)]. The TG curves of MoO_2^{VI} and UO_2^{VI} complexes do not show any weight loss up to 220 °C, indicating the absence of any water molecules in them i.e. lattice or coordinated water molecules. All the complexes show rapid degradation in the temperature range 400–650 °C. This may be due to the partial decomposition of organic part of the ligand, followed by the rapid fall in the percentage weight loss. The decomposition continues up to ~645 °C in each complex as indicated by the consistency in weight in the plateau of the thermogram and formed stable respective metal oxide. On the basis of half decomposition temperature the thermal stability (Table 2) is found to be in the following order.

The various kinetic and thermodynamic parameters viz. activation energy (E_a), frequency factor (Z), entropy of activation (ΔS), and free energy change (ΔG) for non-isothermal decomposition of metal complexes have been determined by Horowitz-Metzer method. The calculated free energy of activation is relatively low indicating the autocatalytic effect of metal ion on thermal decomposi-

Fig. 1. Thermograms of H_2L and its complexes.

Table 2. Thermal decomposition data of H_2L and its complexes

Compound	Half decomposition temperature (°C)	Activation energy (E_a) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Frequency factor (Z) (s ⁻¹)	Entropy change ($-\Delta S$) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Free energy change (ΔG) (kJ mol ⁻¹)
H_2L	490	80.44	2.77×10^{-9}	238.191	116.635
[VO(L)]. H_2O	450	71.53	3.67×10^{-11}	237.559	106.832
[Mn(L).2 H_2O]	300	64.39	2.37×10^{-9}	229.144	168.681
[Fe(L). H_2O .Cl]	430	70.82	3.65×10^{-7}	242.924	104.382
[Co(L).2 H_2O]	320	83.32	2.47×10^{-8}	176.827	156.496
[Ni(L).2 H_2O]	430	47.54	5.10×10^{-10}	360.056	154.782
[Cu(L).2 H_2O]	390	63.40	4.32×10^{-7}	302.718	118.005
[Zn(L).2 H_2O]	395	85.30	2.81×10^{-8}	164.178	164.766
[Cd(L).2 H_2O]	400	84.18	6.52×10^{-10}	365.439	146.094
[MoO_2 (L)]	370	76.56	4.81×10^{-7}	284.344	105.133
[UO_2 (L)]	340	54.78	3.08×10^{-11}	225.033	176.462

tion of complexes. The entropy of activation (ΔS) is found to be negative, which indicates a more ordered activated state that may be possible through the chemisorptions of oxygen and other decomposition products. The more ordered nature may be due to the polarization of bonds activated state which might happen through charge transfer electronic transitions.

Electrical conductivity measurements :

The solid state electrical conductivity of the ligand and its complexes has been measured in their compressed pellet from ambient temperature to 403 K and values are given in Table 1. The electrical conductivity of complexes increases with increasing in the temperature²⁷. The electrical conductivity (σ) varies experimentally with the absolute temperature according to the relation $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/kT)$ where, σ is conductivity, σ_0 is constant, E_a is the activation energy of electrical conduction, T is the absolute temperature and k is Boltzmann's constant. In the solid state dc electrical conductivity measurements the plot of $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ are found to linear in the studied temperature range indicating that the compounds show typical semiconducting behaviour²⁸ (Fig. 2). The value of electrical conductivities of these compounds lies in the range 3.78×10^{-7} to $7.06 \times 10^{-10} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. The activation energy of electrical conduction of the complexes is found in the range 0.294 to 0.721 eV which indicate their potential to be used as sensitizer for wide band gap semiconductor electrode such as ZnO, TiO₂ and SnO₂ *etc.* a component of dye sensitized photo-electrochemical cells for practical applications such as solar cells *etc.* Low

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of $\log \sigma$.

values of electrical conductivities of the complexes may be due to the weaker intermolecular contact and less extended delocalization of electrons in complexes²⁹.

Antibacterial activity :

The H₂L and its complexes have been screened *in vitro* against the five bacterial strains *i.e.* *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. typhi*, *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis* (Table 3). The Mn^{II} and UO₂^{VI} complexes show maximum antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and whereas moderate acti-

Table 3. Zone of inhibition of growth of microorganism

Compound	Gram-positive bacteria			Gram-negative bacteria	
	<i>E. coli</i> (mm)	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> (mm)	<i>S. typhi</i> (mm)	<i>S. aureus</i> (mm)	<i>B. subtilis</i> (mm)
H ₂ L	8	7	9	10	6
[VO(L)].H ₂ O	13	14	14	15	10
[Mn(L).2H ₂ O]	17	11	15	13	11
[Fe(L).H ₂ O.Cl]	15	17	13	16	14
[Co(L).2H ₂ O]	14.5	16	12	11	13
[Ni(L).2H ₂ O]	12	12	10.5	17	11
[Cu(L).2H ₂ O]	16	15	16	15.5	10
[Zn(L).2H ₂ O]	13	14	12	16	9.5
[Cd(L).2H ₂ O]	10.5	17	15	15	13
[MoO ₂ (L)]	16	15	13	17.5	11
[UO ₂ (L)]	17	16	15	15	14

vity towards all other bacterial strains. The complexes of Fe^{III} and Cd^{II} show good antibacterial activity against *P. aeruginosa* and moderate activity against other bacterial strains. The Ni^{II} and MoO_2^{VI} complexes exhibited high antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* bacteria. The complexes of VO^{IV} , Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} show considerable biological activity against all the selected bacterial strains. All the complexes show good activity as compared to the H_2L against all the Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains. It has been observed that the metal complexes show enhanced antibacterial activity as compared to the free ligand against the same organism under identical experimental conditions. This is because of the chelation. According to Tweedy's chelation theory³⁰, the chelation reduces the polarity of the metal atom mainly because of the partial sharing of its positive charge with donor groups and possible π electron delocalisation over the whole ring. This increases the lipophilic character of the metal chelate which favours its permeating through the lipid layer of bacterial membranes.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents used as starting materials for the synthesis of ligand and its metal complexes were of analytical grade. The metal salts used for preparation of complexes i.e. vanadyl sulphate pentahydrates ($\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$), manganese acetate dihydrate [$\text{Mn}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$], anhydrous ferric chloride [FeCl_3], cobalt acetate dihydrate [$\text{Co}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$], nickel acetate dihydrate [$\text{Ni}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$], copper acetate dihydrate [$\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$], zinc acetate dihydrate [$\text{Zn}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$] and uranyl acetate dihydrate [$\text{UO}_2(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$] were commercially available and used as received. Dioxomolybdenum acetate(VI) dihydrate was prepared from ammonium molybdate by known method³¹. The solvents were used after their distillation by standard method³².

Synthesis of ligand (H_2L) :

The Schiff base ligand was synthesized in two steps. In the first steps the preparation of 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone, while in the second step the condensation of the 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone with carbohydrazone have been made.

Synthesis of 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone carbohydrazone (H_2L) :

A solution of carbohydrazone (1.8 g, 0.02 mol) in EtOH-DMF was added to a solution of 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone (3.42 g, 0.02 mol) in EtOH at 50 °C over a period of 10 min. The reaction mixture was refluxed on oil bath for about 7 h. On cooling to room temperature, the dark brown coloured product obtained was filtered off, washed with ethanol, petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo* over CaCl_2 . Yield 78%, m.p. 248 °C (Fig. 3).

$^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 12.40 (2H, s, phenolic OH), 11.55 (2H, s, imino NH), 2.75 (6H, s, methyl), 6.9–7.5 ppm (6H, m, Ar-H); FAB-MASS (m/z) 395 (MH^+) [$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_2$], m/z 397 ($\text{M}+2$)⁺.

Synthesis of complexes :

Equimolar quantities (0.01 mol) of Schiff base ligand and appropriate metal salt were dissolved separately in DMF (25 ml) and ethanol respectively and mixed them in hot condition under continuous stirring. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 6–8 h on an oil bath. On cooling to room temperature, the colored complexes precipitated out was filtered, washed with alcohol, DMF and petroleum ether and finally dried under vacuum at room temperature. Yield : 65–75%.

Antibacterial screening using agar cup-plate method :

Antibacterial activity of the ligand and its complexes was carried out against the bacteria, *E. coli*, *S. abony*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa* and *B. subtilis* by cup plate

Fig. 3. Synthesis of Schiff base ligand.

method³³. Peptone 10 g, NaCl 5 g, beef extract 3 g, nutrient agar 15 g, was used as the medium. The sterile molten medium held at 55 °C was poured aseptically into sterile petri dishes and allowed to solidify. After solidification, 24 h culture (incubated at 37 °C) of each of the bacterial culture was spread on the agar medium with the help of a glass spreader. Then with a sterile cork borer (8 mm dia.), cups were punched and scooped out from the agar at suitable distances from each other. The cups were filled with 0.1 mL of the test solutions (10 mg mL⁻¹ in DMSO); and DMSO as the control. The plates were incubated upright at 37 °C for 24 h before reading the inhibition zones around each cup.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analysis carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were obtained using Carlo Erba 1108 analyser in Micro Analytical Laboratory, SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 597 spectrophotometer using KBr pallets at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh. ¹H NMR spectrum of ligand was obtained using a Bruker Auance-II 400 NMR spectrophotometer in DMSO solvent at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh. The reflectance spectra of the complexes were recorded on Varian SE UV-NIR spectrophotometer at RSIC, IIT, Chennai using MgO as reference. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by Gouy's method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as a calibrant and the diamagnetic corrections were made by using Pascal's constants. The solid state dc electrical conductivity of compounds was measured by Zentech Electrometer in their compressed pellet form over 313–403 K temperature range. TG analysis of the complexes was carried out on Perkin-Elmer TG-2 thermobalance in ambient air with a heating rate of 10 °C per minute. Metal contents of the complexes were analysed gravimetrically after decomposing the complexes with a mixture of HClO₄, H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ and then igniting to metal oxide. The FAB mass of ligand was recorded on a JEOL SX102 mass spectrometer, at SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow, using Argon/Xenon (6 KV, 10 MA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was kept at 10 kV, *m*-nitro benzyl alcohol (NBA) was used as the matrix.

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